

Minutes of the 59th Experimenters' Meeting The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 22nd June 2017

(This document was finalised on 29th January 2018)

Present:

(BA)	Dr Bogdan Antonescu ⁵	
(CG)	Dr Catherine Gaffard ²	
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ⁴	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{3,4}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ⁴	
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{1,4}	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁵	Chair
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁵	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ³	
(ZL)	Dr Zhihong Li ²	

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAR	National Center for Atmospheric Research
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
PMSE	Polar Mesosphere Summer Echoes
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	Universal Time
VSWR	voltage standing wave ratio
v3/v4	MST Radar processing versions 3/4

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 58th meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 57.1.1 DAH and CJW [Chris Walden] to put together a work plan to ensure that a new MST radar signal processing scheme is ready by the time of the next (58th) Experimenters' meeting.

COMPLETED

In connection with the three action items above, DAH reported that he had released the first version 4 data files and that he would soon begin reprocessing the archive. He will report on this in section 4g.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

DAH and CJW have discussed getting another member of RAL staff, who is already working with Campbell Scientific data loggers, to take over this task. GV emphasised that this should be given high priority since the surface wind dataset is one of the most commonly used datasets.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

DAH will report on progress with laser ceilometer data in section 4d.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

No progress has been made on the Met Office's model-comparison statistics.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

DISCONTINUED

ACTION ITEM 58.1.1 DAH to consult with members of the data user community in order to establish the sort of instrument performance details that would be useful.

ONGOING

Action item 53.4.2 was considered to be superseded by 58.1.1 and so has been discontinued. GAP suggested that the a file containing instrument performance details should sit alongside the main data files and could be updated whenever necessary. Ideally the details would be included within the main data files. However, it was acknowledged that some issues might not be known about until after the data files have been created.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.2 GAP to assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to the NERC MSTRF's Vaisala WXT510 dataset.

ONGOING

GAP reported that this WXT510 dataset was currently under review within CEDA and that the DOIs will be issued in the near future. He is in the process of tidying up deprecated MST Radar datasets, i.e. versions 0 - 3, and thinks that DOIs could be assigned to those ones that are no longer being updated.

ACTION ITEM 58.4.1 DAH to prioritise the release of the latest surface met data to CEDA.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that this had been completed. More details are given in section 4a.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP gave a report on the how the MSTRF's data have been accessed through the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA). These statistics are publicly visible through http://public-stats.ceda.ac.uk/cgi-bin/stats/download_stats_public.py?selpath=%2Fbadc%2Fmst%2F. CEDA has recently changed its web download service as the old one was found to be under-reporting usage. There were 51 users during the past 6 months, with a similar spread in user types as reported at the last meeting. The number of people accessing quicklook plots has risen to 390. Some people have been accessing deprecated MST radar data files, i.e. from version 2 and earlier. GAP has modified the corresponding catalogue pages to alert users to the existence of improved data products. Moreover, he is planning to reorganise the archives of MST radar data products, so that they fit into a more-logical directory structure.

DAH reported that all MSTRF data files now pass through a quarantine area before being delivered to the CEDA archive. This allows him to inspect the corresponding quick look plots and to remove any data files that contain unrealistic-looking data. The "history" global attribute of accepted netCDF files is automatically updated with an entry reading, "*data passed visual quality control check and file delivered to CEDA for ingestion into archives*". The quarantine system leads to a delay in data files (but not quick look plots) becoming available. Although this will typically be only a few hours, longer delays will occur over weekends and when DAH is on leave. GAP added that it is possible to create password-protected areas on jasmin. This could be used to allow access to quarantined data files for users who want access to them as quickly as possible, e.g. during campaign periods.

3b) Electricity - DAH

Work on the the MSTRF's electrical distribution system required all equipment to be powered down between approximately 9 am and 5 pm on 7th and 8th March 2017. The primary task was to consolidate an earlier makeshift repair to one of the main distribution cables. A statutory electrical inspection was carried out at the same time. Owing to the government's restrictions on which companies can now undertake "facilities management" work, it took DAH a year to get the contract set up.

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units experienced only four short-lived input power problems during the past 6 months: once on 27th May 2017 and three times on 6th June. There appears to have been a 15 minute outage starting at 22:04 UTC on 30th April 2017. Although the beam steering computer (tiberius) does not appear to have shut down, it failed to respond between 22:16 and 22:21 UTC.

This led to a gap of 291 s between the 3rd and 4th dwells of the MST radar observation cycle that began at 22:15:09 UTC.

UPS unit TXA generated repeated inverter fault messages on 3rd and 4th April 2017. LD switched to a spare battery pack and a new pack has been ordered.

3c) Telecommunications

During the past 6 months there was one loss of internet connection to the radar site - between approximately 05:20 and 13:50 UTC on Saturday 27th May 2017. DAH was attending the MST15 conference in Japan at the time. Since he was 8 hours ahead of UK time, he spotted the problem early on and was able to alert LD. Moreover, since he could see that a deep convection system had been crossing the radar site at the time of the last plot update, he was able to recommend that LD look out for signs of lightning-related damage. The connection was restored after LD changed a phone/internet filter.

3d) Miscellaneous

There were two student visits to the radar site during the past 6 months. Masters students from Aberystwyth University carried out their surveying practical on the MST radar antenna array on 28th March 2017. Environmental Science undergraduates from the University of Manchester visited the site on 25th April 2017 as part of a wider field trip to Wales. Since there was widespread cumulonimbus cloud development throughout the day, DAH focussed his presentation on deep convection.

Also on 25th April 2017, the site's septic tank was emptied - possibly for the first time in its 25 lifetime. Amazingly, it had not quite filled to capacity. When NERC carried out surveys of all their sites during the second half of 2016, they had identified the septic tank as something that would need to be replaced. They also identified a number of other estates' issues that would need to be dealt with within the next 5 years. They decided to award the MSTRF a lump sum for these combined works in January 2017. However, since there was no way that DAH would have been able to spend all of the money before the end of the financial year (RAL does not allow income to be rolled over from one year to the next), the money was paid to the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) in Leeds.

When the septic tank was emptied, which cost £150, it was deemed to be in a good condition and so won't need to be replaced, for which NERC had budgeted £15k. GV has been given permission by NERC to spend the surplus money on other estates' issues. He urged DAH to focus on clearing the MST radar's antenna array of willow saplings, which are growing out of control. He recommended that DAH seek the help of the estates specialists within RAL, since this job would fall under the category of "facilities management" rules. DAH also reported that many of the stanchions supporting the MST radar antennas were showing signs of rust. This appears to be the result of two different metals being in contact. The stanchions were painted rather than being galvanised.

ACTION ITEM 59.3.1 DAH to arrange for the clearance of willow saplings from the MST radar's antenna array as soon as possible.

NEW

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

The delivery of formatted data files to CEDA was interrupted in August 2015 when the computer that DAH had been using was decommissioned. DAH has been in the process, ever since, of rewriting the file creation software to run on jasmin. This has led to variable delays in data availability being resumed. The collection of raw data has carried on as before.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

NASA Ames data files have been made available again through CEDA since April 2017 - refer to main

comment for section 4. DAH has begun making use of the raw data files from the Vaisala WXT520 (see below) in order to establish whether or not the Campbell Scientific tipping bucket raingauge might have become blocked. This led to LD cleaning out the tipping bucket on 9th June 2017, when it was found to contain a build-up of algae, a slug, and an ants' nest. The NASA Ames files for 5th - 9th June, inclusive, were not released into the CEDA archive for this reason.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

The availability of NASA Ames data files was resumed in December 2015. There have been no problems with data from these sensors within the past 6 months. GV wondered whether it would be worth adding a sonic anemometer to the tower when DAH replaces the data logger - see action item action item 51.4.1. DAH pointed out that the biggest limitation of the Frongoch site was that the MSTRF no longer had guaranteed access to it since it had no official links with Aberystwyth University. GV pointed out that David Wareing was still officially a member of the University's staff.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

Formatted data from this instrument are not yet available. Refer to the main comment for section 4 and to section 4a.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

Raw data were not collected between 20th and 21st April 2017 as a result of an unrelated program encountering a problem on the acquisition computer. Formatted data from this instrument are not yet available - refer to the main comment for section 4. Nevertheless, DAH aims to make progress with the file creation software over the summer. He will be supervising a vacation student, who will need access to the data for a project looking at the signature of clouds seen by the MST radar.

GV suggested that it would be useful to install a new Luft ceilometer at the MST radar site if capital money could be found. Luft are developing a two channel instrument that allows the linear depolarisation ratio to be derived. This significantly extends the scientific usefulness of the observations.

DK asked whether observations made by one of the RAL-designed cloud radars would be useful for DAH's vacation student project. A development instrument has been in operation at Cardington for the past year and a half, whilst the Met Office's own instrument has been deployed elsewhere. It does not yet have Doppler capability and despite still having some technical issues, it can provide good observations. GAP suggested that the data could be made available through CEDA.

4e) Sky Cameras

DAH will be publishing several new time lapse videos from the first sky camera in the near future. He will not make images from the second sky camera available until he has decided on the most appropriate way to apply the Dublin Core metadata scheme to them. The same applies to images taken by the Noctilucent Cloud camera - see below.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH began summer season observations early, on 22nd May 2017, since he was away between 24th May and 6th June at the MST15 conference.

4g) MST Radar

DAH began by presenting model-comparison statistics for the past six months, which had been prepared by Caroline Bulpitt of the Met Office. The number of observations received daily by the EUMETNET Composite Observing System (EUCOS) was fairly constant over the period. However, there were at least 4 days during March and April 2017 when this dropped by more than half. Two of these days (7th and 8th March) were associated with planned radar down time for electrical work (see section 3b). The EUCOS root mean square (RMS) wind mean vector difference values only exceeded the 5.0 m s^{-1}

target maximum on one day. The Met Office's UKV model-comparison statistics also show good data quality over the period, with no significant changes from the previous six month period.

DAH then gave a general instrument performance report. The transmitters have been relatively reliable over the past six months. TXA only had a blown fuse on two occasions and TXB on three. TXB experienced one analogue error and TXC experienced two. Beam steering unit 28 began reporting slightly elevated voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) values on 5th May 2017. The radar was stopped on the morning of 7th May so that LD could swap the unit. However, the VSWR value went up. Consequently the radar was stopped again an hour later and LD replaced the feed to the antenna that was giving slightly unusual readings with a dummy load.

Version 3 (v3) Cartesian files for 14th and 23rd April 2017 were not allowed into the data archive. Both showed unrealistically fast wind speeds within limited time/altitude regions. The cause of the contamination is unknown.

DAH reported that he had released the first version 4 (v4) "Cardinal" files to CEDA in mid April 2017. These are broadly similar to the v3 Cartesian files, but contain time-averaged horizontal wind components and use these for applying beam-broadening correction to vertical beam spectral widths. This improves data quality. More details can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/mst_v4_signal_processing.html. At present v4 files are only available for recent campaign periods, i.e. covering NAWDEX and the dates for Graeme Marlton's turbulence measurements. Other dates can be reprocessed on request. GV noted that although the sample v4 files were not yet compliant with the latest NCAS data standards, they were good enough to be released. Consequently DAH should reprocess the entire observation archive back to 2011, i.e. to the time of the replacement of the beam steering units, as soon as possible. DAH pointed out that the poor state of the beam steering units before this had caused the aspect sensitivity, and therefore the associated wind speed compensation factor, to be unrealistically large. GV thought, nevertheless, that earlier dates should also be reprocessed. NCAS-compliant standards can be adopted for the next version of the files.

ACTION ITEM 59.4.1 DAH to create v4 Cardinal files for all dates back to mid 2011 as soon as possible.

NEW

5. Guest Instrument Report

GV reported that the Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler (BLWP) has been operated in Portugal since the end of April 2017. It is supporting an observation campaign organised by the US National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). The aim has been to look at wind flow over a partially complex terrain with a view to creating a European wind atlas. The scale of instrumentation was vast, incorporating 41 flux towers and 28 wind-measuring lidars. GV had not known anything about the campaign in advance. NCAR had made contact through the Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF), effectively looking to hire the BLWP rather than to find a scientific partner. GV nevertheless thought that it was an interesting project to be involved with. On this occasion, the BLWP had been put on the back of a lorry rather than being towed by the Land Rover. This turned out to be a preferable way to transport it. The BLWP will return to the MSTRF at the end of June 2017. One of the aims is to continue making co-located observations with the MST radar, following on from Chris Lee's work. This work will continue to make use of "windsonds", which are a light-weight and easier-to-use alternative to standard radiosondes - see minutes of 58th meeting for more details.

The Elight lidar is working well, although the Raman lidar and ozone lidar have been suffering from problems. GV plans to have another student analysing lidar data over the summer. He is particularly interested in the fact that the lidars within the Met Office's network were able to detect aerosols from

the recent forest fires in Portugal. GAP expressed an interest in any new datasets that could be archived by CEDA.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Wind profiler backscatter signal monitoring - CG

CG presented work that she and ZL have been undertaking in order to assess the suitability of BLWP echo power for assimilation into the Met Office's UKV numerical weather prediction scheme. Based on the assumption that Bragg scattering is the predominant radar return mechanism, the echo power is expected to depend on the vertical structures of temperature and humidity. These are two of the most important measures of atmospheric state and hourly model values can be used to predict the echo power. It was easy to find instances for which there was a good agreement between the modelled and observed values (although the features generated by the model were generally less sharp than the observed ones or those predicted from radiosonde data). These were typically associated with clear-sky/fair-weather conditions. However, the scatter plots based on two-and-a-half years' worth of data showed a poor overall correlation between the observed and model values and between the observed and radiosonde values (the correlation between model and radiosonde values was noticeably better). CG and ZL tried various approaches to improve the correlations, e.g. ignoring cloudy situations. However, this did not significantly change the pattern.

GV pointed out that the gradient terms for the predicted echo power were highly sensitive to the vertical scale over which they were evaluated. He suggested using an adaptive scale. The present work was based on data from the Camborne BLWP, which does not have a vertical beam. CG and ZL are keen to examine data from the Wattisham BLWP, which does. This will allow them to test whether or not the scatter is isotropic, as expected. They are also keen to look at data from the wind-profiler at Lindenberg, since it has a co-located Raman lidar. This will remove any issues associated with the horizontal separation between radar and radiosonde measurements.

6b) Radar wind profile at sea - DK

This presentation is based on work that DK has undertaken under the auspices of his own company rather than as a member of RAL staff. The aim is to improve the global measurement of winds. Such measurements can already be undertaken from satellites by tracking the movement of cloud tops or sea surface waves. However, the former technique cannot be applied under cloud-free conditions and the latter (when based on optical methods) cannot be applied under cloudy conditions. Moreover, even under optimal conditions, these techniques only provide winds at between two and four altitude levels and they have low re-visit rates. Although radar wind profilers, such as BLWPs and MST radars, are well established for use on land, they have only rarely been used at sea and never in an operational capacity. In order to make such observations, elaborate stabilisation platforms are needed in order to compensate for movements of the observing platform. DK presented his proposed methods for overcoming these limitations.

6c) Twelve years of mesospheric observations from Aberystwyth - DAH

DAH repeated a presentation that he had first given at the recent MST15 conference. During the earliest years of the MST radar's operation (i.e. the early 1990s), mesospheric observations were made on a fairly frequent, albeit non-systematic, basis using multiple beam pointing directions. Most of these observations were confined to the mid-summer months and to the hours between 09 and 15 UTC. They ceased to be made in the late 1990s. DAH re-introduced mesospheric observations in April 2005, but this time on a systematic basis and using only the vertical beam pointing direction - once every 5 minutes.

It was already known that the echoes observed during the mid-summer months are similar in nature to the Polar Mesosphere Summer Echoes (PMSEs) observed at higher latitudes. Compared to mesospheric echoes observed at other times of year, PMSEs are significantly stronger, more-frequently occurring, of

longer duration, and occur at slightly higher altitudes. They are known to rely on the existence of ice crystals, which can be seen in the form of Noctilucent Clouds if they grow sufficiently large. DAH's analysis of the long-term Aberystwyth dataset shows that there is much more of an overlap between the characteristics of summer season and non summer season echoes than he had previously suspected. This suggests that not all of the echoes observed during the summer season are of the PMSE type, i.e. that they do not rely on the presence of ice crystals. Outside of the mid-summer months, there is no fixed pattern of mesospheric echo occurrence and there is considerable variability in prevalence from year to year. A few rare echoes, during both summer and non summer seasons, defy the traditional explanation by occurring during non-sunlit hours.

7. Any Other Business

The date of the next meeting was provisionally set for late January 2018.